

Enhancing Cancer Subtype Classification through Convolutional Neural Networks: A DeepInsight Analysis of TCGA Gene Expression Data

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Abstract

Purpose: This study investigates the adaptation of DeepInsight for cancer subtype classification using high-dimensional gene expression data. Originally designed for non-image data, DeepInsight has been adapted for cancer classification.

Methods: We evaluated DeepInsight's performance against several models, including support vector machines, LightGBM, neural networks, and decision trees, with and without the application of the Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique. The study utilized gene expression data from breast, lung, and colon cancers. A novel multi-class feature selection method was introduced, using modified aggregated class activation maps to identify key genes across different cancer subtypes. These critical genes were further analyzed through Gene Ontology to explore their roles in significant biological processes.

Result: DeepInsight consistently outperformed traditional models in terms of F1 score across breast, lung, and colon cancer datasets, effectively addressing multi-class classification challenges. Notably, several top genes were identified as significant across multiple methods. Furthermore, we conducted a Gene Ontology analysis on the critical genes, including the top genes identified by DeepInsight and the common genes recognized through multiple methods.

Conclusion: The adaptation of DeepInsight provides an approach to cancer subtype classification by transforming high-dimensional gene expression data into image representations. Utilizing aggregated class activation maps, it effectively identifies critical pixels within these images, enabling the discovery of distinct genes that may not be highlighted by other methods. DeepInsight demonstrates potential as a valuable tool for classifying cancer subtypes and critical genes.

Keywords: DeepInsight, Cancer Subtype Classification, Convolutional Neural Networks, Gene Expression Data, Comparative Study

1 Introduction

In oncology, accurate classification of cancer subtypes is crucial for advancing personalized medicine, allowing for treatment strategies that are tailored to the specific genetic characteristics of tumors. The advent of machine learning has propelled this field forward, offering sophisticated tools to dissect the complex molecular landscapes of cancers. Among these, some studies have used machine learning to refine breast cancer subtype classification, showcasing the potential of non-invasive techniques to improve diagnostic precision and treatment specificity [1, 2]. The utilization of machine learning extends beyond breast cancer. The applications in lung and hematopoietic cancers underline the versatility of deep learning in differentiating subtypes and extracting disease-defining features, reinforcing the model’s utility in a broad spectrum of cancer research [3, 4].

Recent advancements, including using Bayesian deep learning applied to whole-genome sequencing data, have shown promise in pinpointing critical genetic markers [5]. With the development of neural networks (NNs) and deep learning, models developed specifically based on them are emerging as well. Among them, the DCGN framework, a deep learning model combining convolutional neural networks (CNN) and bidirectional gated recurrent units (BiGRU), excels in cancer subtype classification. It addresses challenges such as data sparsity and imbalance, achieving superior accuracy and generalization [6].

Despite advancements in machine learning, challenges remain in classifying cancer subtypes from high-dimensional gene expression data. Traditional methods, such as SVM and LightGBM, treat genes as independent features, struggling with the complexity of gene interactions. However, recent techniques, such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs) applied through DeepInsight,

leverage t-SNE [7] to transform high-dimensional gene expression data into interpretable 2D images. This transformation enables CNNs to capture the relationships between genes, addressing the limitation of traditional methods by revealing deeper insights into gene interactions and improving classification performance.

In this study, we evaluated each method with and without SMOTE [8], assessing model performance using the F1 score. SMOTE improved precision and F1 scores in some cases though at the cost of increased computational demands. Despite these trade-offs, we retained SMOTE as it helped balance the dataset by addressing class imbalances. This balancing improved the model’s sensitivity to underrepresented subtypes, making gene selection more reliable and inclusive of genes relevant to the minority class. Ignoring these minority subtypes could lead to missed therapeutic opportunities or inaccurate prognoses.

We modified the DeepInsight program to enable the identification and output of the top genes implicated in cancer subtypes across all classes—an enhancement that was previously unavailable. DeepInsight is an effective approach for classifying cancer subtypes, utilizing its unique ability to transform tabular data into image representations. This transformation process, while facilitating classification, can result in a degree of information loss, limiting its suitability for directly identifying the most critical genes associated with cancer subtypes. Consequently, the transformation process may lead DeepInsight to emphasize distinct genes that may not fully capture their true significance in differentiating cancer subtypes. To improve interpretability, we performed Gene Ontology analysis on common genes identified by multiple methods, as well as the top 20 genes selected by DeepInsight. This targeted analysis enhances the biological understanding of these genes and provides a more comprehensive evaluation of their roles in cancer subtypes.

Table 1 Summary of the datasets.

Datasets	#samples	#features	#classes
Breast Cancer	981	19,738	5
Lung Cancer	966	19,219	2
Colon Cancer	341	17,496	4

Table 2 Distribution of Cancer Subtypes in Dataset.

Datasets	Subtypes
Breast Cancer	LumA: 50.9%
	LumB: 20.1%
	Basal: 17.4%
	Her2: 8.0%
	Normal: 3.7%
Lung Cancer	LUAD: 52.0%
	LUSC: 48.0%
Colon Cancer	CIN: 66.3%
	MS: 17.6%
	GS: 14.4%
	POLE: 1.8%

2 Experimental Data

Gene expression data for this study was sourced from The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) [9] through cBioPortal [10]. Data normalization was performed using RNA-Seq by Expectation Maximization (RSEM) [11], and the results were standardized as z-scores relative to normal tissue samples to ensure cross-sample comparability.

We focused on three major cancer types—breast, lung, and colon cancer—due to their high incidence rates and clinical importance in personalized medicine. Including these cancers allows us to evaluate the model’s performance across distinct and biologically complex subtypes. For breast cancer, we analyzed five clinically significant subtypes: Luminal A (LumA), Luminal B (LumB), Basal-like (Basal), HER2, and Normal-like (Normal), as these subtypes represent distinct molecular profiles and treatment responses [12–14]. For lung cancer, our analysis concentrated on Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer (NSCLC) subtypes, specifically Lung Adenocarcinoma (LUAD) and Lung Squamous Cell Carcinoma (LUSC), while excluding Small Cell Lung Cancer (SCLC) due

to insufficient gene expression data in TCGA. For colon cancer, the subtypes analyzed were Chromosomal Instability (CIN), Microsatellite Instability (MSI), Genomically Stable (GS), and Polymerase Epsilon (POLE) mutation. The datasets analyzed are outlined in Tables 1 and 2.

2.1 Data Processing and Splitting

Figure 1 illustrates our workflow for cancer subtype classification, showing the data processing steps and how the data is utilized in both traditional machine learning models and the DeepInsight framework, including the top identified genes and a comparison of F1 scores. The top 20 genes associated with each cancer type are detailed in tables in Appendix B, the metrics like F1 scores are provided in Tables in Appendix A.

To evaluate model performance, we tested seven train-test split ratios, starting with 10% for testing and incrementally increasing to 30% in 5% steps, followed by 10% steps up to 70%. This allowed us to assess the sensitivity of models to varying training data sizes. For each ratio, we performed five fittings using predetermined random seeds, with the test set for a lower ratio being a subset of the following higher ratio. This ensured consistent evaluation and minimized variability from random splits and initialization. We also conducted experiments for each method with and without SMOTE, with performance differences detailed in Tables in Appendix A.

3 Machine Learning Models for Cancer Subtype Classification

Several machine learning models (as outlined in Section 3.2) were applied for cancer subtype classification alongside the DeepInsight framework. All experiments were conducted on Google Colab, utilizing an NVIDIA A100 GPU with 40 GB of GPU RAM and 83.5 GB of system RAM. Performance metrics, such as F1 scores, were averaged over five runs using fixed random seeds.

3.1 DeepInsight Methodology

We used DeepInsight to transform gene expression data into a pixel-based format for CNN analysis. Initially, feature scaling, as described in DeepInsight [15], was applied to both the training and testing datasets, normalizing each feature between 0 and 1 based on its observed minimum and maximum values in the training data. The normalization process is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} X_{tr_norm}(j, :) &= \frac{X_{tr}(j, :) - \text{Min}_j}{\text{Max}_j - \text{Min}_j} \\ X_{test_norm}(j, :) &= \frac{X_{test}(j, :) - \text{Min}_j}{\text{Max}_j - \text{Min}_j} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

After normalization, the training set was transposed to align features as rows, each representing a sample, thereby forming a revised feature set. This step utilized the training set to pinpoint the exact coordinates of features, essential for subsequent image transformation. We then applied t-SNE which the distance metric is set to cosine to this set, projecting the features onto a 2D plane with similar features clustered. The reason for using dimensionality reduction techniques such as t-SNE before transforming the data into images is that this approach emphasizes the critical importance of spatial coherence (i.e., the pixels close to each other share similar information) among pixels for CNNs which rely on the arrangement and proximity of pixels to extract meaningful patterns from images to ensure its performance. The resulting spatial arrangement was encapsulated within the smallest possible rectangle and subsequently aligned horizontally or vertically via rotation for optimal CNN processing [15]. This approach enhances classification accuracy and generalization by revealing subtle, biologically relevant patterns in gene expression, unlike traditional methods like SVM or LightGBM, which treat genes as independent features.

Furthermore, the Cartesian coordinates were converted into pixel values by averaging highly similar features into single pixels. Each sample of the training and testing sets was then mapped using these coordinates to create its corresponding

feature matrix. All the feature matrices are transformed into images in RGB format (see Fig. 2). In this format, each pixel has three channels representing the intensity of red, green, and blue light. In our study, every individual feature value was assigned to all three channels of its corresponding pixel, resulting in grayscale images. For consistency, breast and lung cancer images were rendered at 224x224 pixels, while colon cancer images were set at 400x200 pixels for Deepinsight method.

After obtaining the image data, the ResNet26d model, a modified ResNet architecture, was used to classify cancer subtypes from the generated images (Fig. 3). The network starts with an input layer, followed by convolutional blocks with 2D convolution, ReLU activation, batch normalization, and skip connections. The final layer outputs probability scores for each subtype, with the highest score determining the predicted class. ResNet’s architecture optimizes learning by shortening gradient paths, leading to faster convergence and more efficient training. The model was trained for 100, 80, and 50 epochs on the breast, colon, and lung cancer datasets, respectively. In addition, the batch size is set to 16, the optimizer used is stochastic gradient descent (SGD) with a learning rate of 0.001, and the momentum is set to 0.9. All parameters were chosen on the basis of cross-validation to optimize performance.

For top gene selection, we employed DeepInsight’s **DeepFeature** method, which utilizes Class Activation Maps (CAMs)-based feature selection to identify the most significant genes for distinguishing between cancer subtypes [15]. Unlike traditional single-class CAM methods focusing on individual subtypes, our approach introduces a multi-class feature selection method by aggregating CAMs across all subtypes. By aggregating feature importance from all classes, we selected the top N features by pinpointing the indices of features corresponding to coordinates on the CAM that exceed a defined threshold. This approach allows us to identify genes that are consistently significant across multiple subtypes (see Algorithm 1 and 2).

Fig. 1 Gene Expression Data Analysis Workflow: From Preprocessing to Model Comparison.

Algorithm 1 DeepFeature (Part 1): This algorithm presents the process for calculating aggregated activations, with modifications highlighted in red to show the changes.

```

1: function compute_cam( $X, y$ )
2:   for each input image and its label in  $X, y$  do
3:     Pre-process the image using imageTransformer
4:     Compute the CAM using the specified cam-Method and targetLayer
5:     Store the CAM output
6:   end for
7:   return The CAM output
8: end function

9: function calculate_aggregated_activations( $X, y$ )
10:  Use compute_cam to generate CAMs for all images in  $X, y$ 
11:  Aggregate these CAMs using a specified method (e.g., mean) to get a single CAM representation
12:  return Aggregated CAMs
13: end function

```

Algorithm 2 DeepFeature (Part 2, continued): Feature selection based on aggregated CAMs.

```

1: function select_top_features(aggregated_cam, topN, threshold)
2:   Initialize an empty list for top features
3:   for each feature in aggregated_cam do
4:     if feature activation  $\geq$  threshold then
5:       Add feature to the top features list
6:     end if
7:   end for
8:   Sort top features based on activation strength
9:   return The top N features
10: end function

```

DeepInsight was trained on full datasets for each cancer type, using activation thresholds of 0.545 for breast cancer, 0.696 for colon cancer, and 0.948 for lung cancer. Genes with activation values above these thresholds were considered top genes,

Fig. 2 Two of the five breast cancer subtypes sample images with resolution 224×224 were obtained using DeepInsight. The images, which are in RGB format, display identical values across all colour channels, making them grayscale. Features within these images are represented as white points against a black background, with the brightness indicating the feature's value.

with the top 20 genes identified for each threshold based on the CAMs used in the analysis.

3.2 Other Machine Learning Methods

In our comparative analysis, DeepInsight was evaluated alongside several well-established machine learning models, selected for their effectiveness in classification. The models included a SVM with a Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel, a regularization parameter $C=3$ to balance margin maximization and classification accuracy, and `probability=True` to enable probabilistic outputs.

LightGBM, optimized for multi-class classification with adjustments for class imbalance and minimizing logarithmic loss, using 'gbdt' boosting with 50 leaves, a learning rate of 0.05, and feature

and bagging fractions of 0.9 and 0.8, respectively; NNs with a layered architecture (2500, 1000, 500, 250, 125, and 60 units) employing GELU activation, L2 regularization (factor of $1e-10$), and Dropout layers (rate of 0.5); DCGN starts with a 1024-unit Dense layer (L2-regularized) and reshapes output to $32 \times 32 \times 1$. It then applies two Conv2D layers (128 and 64 filters, 3×3 , "same" padding, stride 2), each followed by 2×2 max pooling, interleaved with a Bidirectional GRU (64 units) with bias and activity regularization. Finally, three Dense layers (with L2 regularization and GELU activations), two Dropout layers (0.6 and 0.7), and a 5-unit softmax output complete the model; in addition, both of NNs and DCGN are trained using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.001 with a batch size of 16; and Decision Trees using Gini impurity for splitting,

Fig. 3 The ResNet Model: The input consists of 2D images generated from gene expression data, processed through the ResNet26D architecture. After convolutional processing, the features are pooled and passed to a fully connected (FC) layer for final cancer subtype classification.

a maximum depth of 20, and splits based on the square root of the number of features. All of these parameters were chosen through cross-validation to achieve the best performance of the methods.

We also applied these models using their built-in functions in Python to select the top genes for each cancer subtype. In SVM, feature importance is extracted using the model coefficients from the `OneVsRestClassifier`. For NNs and DCGN, we used Integrated Gradients to quantify each feature’s contribution. LightGBM determines feature importance using `feature_importance` function, whereas decision trees measure feature significance with the built-in `feature_importances_` attribute, based on the impact of features at each split.

4 Results and Discussion

The performance of each model in classifying breast, lung, and colon cancer subtypes is presented in Tables of Appendix A. Five evaluation metrics are considered: accuracy, precision, F1 score, AUC, and computing time across varying train-test split ratios. Oversampling via SMOTE was applied to the breast and colon cancer datasets, where imbalanced classes are present,

but not to the relatively balanced lung cancer data. In breast and colon cancer, SMOTE generally improves precision, particularly for models such as DeepInsight and DCGN although this benefit comes at the cost of increased computational time. However, in some models like SVM, introducing SMOTE may lead to slight reductions in some metrics, such as accuracy, as the model may overweight synthetic patterns that do not generalize well to unseen data.

We chose the F1 score as the primary evaluation criterion because it balances precision and recall, making it more reliable than accuracy in imbalanced datasets. This is particularly important in cancer subtype classification, where accounting for both false positives and false negatives helps prevent misclassifications that could lead to missed diagnoses or inappropriate treatments.

The best F1 scores for breast, colon, and lung cancer classification are presented in Table 3, comparing various models with and without SMOTE at different train-test ratios. DeepInsight consistently delivered the highest F1 scores, particularly without SMOTE in breast cancer and with SMOTE in colon cancer. DCGN had a good performance at higher train-test ratios with SMOTE

in breast cancer. SVM performed well at lower train-test ratios without SMOTE, while LightGBM emerged as a leading model at a 0.7 ratio with SMOTE in breast cancer. In lung cancer, DeepInsight and Decision Tree achieved perfect F1 scores across all ratios without SMOTE, demonstrating their effectiveness in this context.

4.1 Impact of Image Resolution on DeepInsight’s Performance

Table 4 provides the performance of DeepInsight for various image resolution indicating when it achieves optimal performance. For breast cancer, the highest F1 score of 88.3% was achieved at a resolution of 224×224 . Lung cancer classification consistently achieved perfect accuracy, precision, F1 score, and AUC across resolutions of 120×120 and higher since it has only two subtypes. For colon cancer, the best F1 score of 89.0% occurred at 224×224 , with performance dropping slightly at higher resolutions. Notably, computational time increased substantially with higher resolutions across all datasets. These results show that the use of very high resolutions can add unnecessary complexity without providing an improvement in performance. This highlights the importance of finding the right resolution to have a good balance between performance and computational efficiency for using DeepInsight.

4.2 Top Genes

We applied SMOTE to balance the dataset and increase the model’s sensitivity to minority subtypes, facilitating the identification of genes associated with less common subtypes in cancer classification. Tables in Appendix B present the top 20 genes selected by SVM, LightGBM, DeepInsight, Decision Trees, NNs, DCGN with SMOTE.

DeepInsight, combined with CAMs, identifies genes relevant across multiple subtypes, capturing biologically significant genes like ACTA2 [16], which might be overlooked by single-subtype approaches. DeepInsight’s selection of distinct top genes stems from its approach of transforming tabular data into 2D images. Although this transformation enables innovative feature representation, it can unintentionally lead to information loss. As a result, DeepInsight tends to prioritize unique sets of features compared to methods that more effectively retain the raw structure of the

data. Nevertheless, this unique perspective can uncover less-studied genes; for instance, DeepInsight identified underexplored candidates such as CHST14, ARHGEF25, and DACT3, which may need further investigation.

Traditional models have also identified critical genes, such as GATA3 [17] selected by LightGBM, which is a well-established marker for luminal tumors in breast cancer. Notably, these methods also identified common genes (summarized in Table 5 and detailed further in Appendix B), including CENPN, which was recognized by both LightGBM and Decision Tree models. CENPN is overexpressed in breast cancer and is known to drive malignant behaviors, such as cell proliferation, migration, and invasion [18]. In contrast, certain genes remain underexplored in breast cancer, such as OR6C1 (recognized by both NNs and DCGN) and LCE6A (recognized by both SVM and NNs). Moreover, genes such as PDX1 (recognized by SVM, NNs, and DCGN) have well-established associations with breast cancer, with its loss of expression potentially contributing to disease progression [19–21]. However, its specific roles across different subtypes have not been fully elucidated, emphasizing the need for further investigation. Similarly, among the common genes identified in lung cancer subtypes, many remain underexplored. For instance, OR11G2 (recognized by both DCGN and Decision Tree models) and ZAN (recognized by both SVM and NNs) require additional research to elucidate their potential contributions to lung cancer subtype differentiation and progression. One common gene, MLH1, identified in colon cancer subtypes by both SVM and LightGBM, has emerged as a critical player. MLH1 is a pivotal component of the DNA mismatch repair pathway, and its dysfunction leads to microsatellite instability-high (MSI-H) tumors [22]. The loss of MLH1 function results in the accumulation of mutations and genomic instability—hallmark features of MSI-H cancers—and serves as a key predictor of response to immune checkpoint inhibitors.

Among these methods, although DCGN does not achieve the highest F1 score or other performance metrics, it demonstrates significant overlaps in gene selection with other models. For breast cancer, DCGN and NNs identified many of the same genes, including the PRAME family

Best F1 Score	Breast		Colon		Lung
	Without SMOTE	With SMOTE	Without SMOTE	With SMOTE	Without SMOTE
0.1	SVM (86%)	DI (87.5%)	SVM (85.1%)	DI (87.5%)	DI & DT (100%)
0.15	DI (89.2%)	DI (87.5%)	SVM (86.4%)	DI (85.4%)	DI & DT (100%)
0.2	DI (86.1%)	DI (87.3%)	DI & SVM (86.7%)	DI (87.1%)	DI & DT (100%)
0.25	DI (86.5%)	DCGN (86.7%)	SVM (85.7%)	DI (88.4%)	DI (100%)
0.3	DI (85.4%)	DI (87.4%)	DI (86.3%)	DI (86.9%)	DI & DT (100%)
0.4	DI (86.2%)	DCGN (86.0%)	SVM (84.5%)	DI (87.1%)	DI (100%)
0.5	DI (85.4%)	DCGN (85.5%)	DI (86.0%)	DI (85.8%)	DI (100%)
0.6	DI (82.3%)	DCGN (85.6%)	DI (83.8%)	DI (84.0%)	DI (100%)
0.7	DI (82.8%)	DCGN (83.7%)	DI (84.1%)	DI (82.6%)	DI (100%)

Table 3 Best F1 Scores for Breast, Colon, and Lung Cancer Across Different Train-Test Ratios. DI refers to DeepInsight, and DT refers to Decision Tree.

(PRAMEF9, PRAMEF18)[23], which is a critical marker for breast cancer prognosis, with high expression associated with aggressive disease characteristics and poorer clinical outcomes. Similarly, in lung cancer, DCGN and SVM selected overlapping genes, such as SNORA56, an overexpressed snoRNA implicated in tumorigenesis and recognized as a promising biomarker for lung cancer diagnosis and prognosis [24].

Furthermore, certain genes that are critical for classifying cancer subtypes were not identified by any of the applied methods. For instance, genes such as EGFR, which have been previously reported as highly associated with lung cancer subtypes [25–27], were not identified in this study. This limitation underscores the need to expand the range of analytical approaches and refine their capabilities to detect well-established markers more effectively.

4.3 Gene Ontology for Top Genes

To further investigate the top genes, we performed Gene Ontology (GO) on the top 20 genes using the g:Profiler web server [28] with default parameters. The analysis encompassed three GO categories: Molecular Function (MF), Cellular Component (CC), and Biological Process (BP). Additionally, we investigated pathway enrichment

through the KEGG database; however, no significant KEGG pathways were identified among these genes. Despite comprehensive evaluation of the top genes from individual methods and all genes collectively, no single approach offered a definitive classification of cancer subtypes from a GO perspective.

This study focused on the top 20 genes from DeepInsight while simultaneously integrating common genes shared across multiple methods (shown in Table 5). This combined strategy provides a nuanced perspective on the shared and unique contributions of these genes to cancer biology, highlighting their potential GO relationship in distinguishing subtypes. In addition, we present the context of GO, providing deeper insights into the functional landscape of these genes.

For breast cancer, Gene Ontology (GO) analysis identified key biological processes, including mesenchyme migration (GO:0090131) and tissue development (GO:0009888), which are closely associated with the epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT). EMT serves as a critical mechanism driving tumor invasiveness and metastasis, particularly in basal-like and HER2-positive subtypes [29–31]. These findings highlight the essential role of EMT in enhancing cellular plasticity and enabling the aggressive progression of these

Datasets	Resolution	Accuracy	Precision	F1 Score	AUC	Computing Time
Breast Cancer	50×50	81.7%	83.9%	82.4%	0.98	241
	120×120	86.8%	88.8%	87.4%	0.98	229
	180×180	86.3%	87.8%	86.6%	0.98	267
	224×224	88.3%	88.8%	88.3%	0.98	291
	250×250	87.3%	88.3%	87.4%	0.99	338
	280×280	85.3%	86.7%	85.8%	0.98	395
	320×320	83.8%	88.1%	85.5%	0.98	450
Lung Cancer	50×50	99.0%	99.0%	99.0%	1.00	95
	120×120	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	1.00	82
	180×180	99.5%	99.5%	99.5%	1.00	91
	224×224	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	1.00	96
	250×250	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	1.00	105
	280×280	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	1.00	116
	320×320	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	1.00	139
Colon Cancer	50×50	78.3%	83.6%	80.6%	0.95	126
	120×120	79.7%	82.4%	80.9%	0.94	93
	180×180	82.6%	84.2%	83.3%	0.94	104
	224×224	87.0%	92.6%	89.0%	0.95	112
	250×250	87.0%	91.5%	88.4%	0.97	123
	280×280	84.1%	89.3%	86.0%	0.96	142
	320×320	81.2%	84.1%	82.4%	0.95	156

Table 4 Impact of Image Resolution on DeepInsight Method Performance in Breast, Lung, and Colon Cancer Classification with a 0.2 Train-Test Split Ratio

Category	Repeat Genes	Top 20 Genes from DeepInsight
Breast	LCE6A, SPRR4, PDX1, AQP12A, SNORA58, OR6C1, PRAMEF18, KRTAP4-12, OR5M9, PRAMEF9, CENPN	CHST14, MYOZ, RAB40A, ARHGEF25, KIF7, LTBP3, NLGN2, ACTG2, HSPB2, LIMS2, SMIM10, GAS6, PNMA8B, SERTAD4-AS1, CRLF1, WTIP, DZIP1L, ACTA2, NOG, TAGLN
Colon	MLH1	C11orf1, LRRC23, SFT2D3, ABHD1, C1orf56, EIF4EBP3, FLJ39653, PRSS30P, PYGB, CELF5, MMP24, ENTPD6, WBSCR28, LINC00910, PFN4, ACTR3C, NEU1, SLC22A3, RALY, FBXL12
Lung	TCF23, ZAN, KRTAP4-1, IQCF6, CATSPER4, SNORA56, VWC2L, ZIM3, PRAMEF12, OR4D1, OR11G2, OPRM1	DACT3, MYL9, JPH2, COL8A1, TIMP3, MATN3, STMN2, OPCML, DIO3, ZNF423, SLC16A2, NRK, LINC00922, FAM55B, PLXNA4, TNN, PLXDC1, AXL, SPX, RSPO3

Table 5 Top 20 genes identified by DeepInsight and repeat genes found across breast, lung, and colon datasets using multiple methods, with SMOTE applied.

subtypes, offering valuable insights into potential therapeutic targets. Figure 4 illustrates the BP context for breast cancer, highlighting the enriched GO terms associated with the top genes and their potential roles in these critical processes.

In lung cancer, the GO term "multicellular organismal process" (GO:0032501) was identified as a key differentiating feature between LUAD and

LUSC, reflecting significant differences in immune response or EMT [32–34]. These differences may provide a foundation for the development of subtype-specific diagnostic tools and treatment strategies. For colon cancer, although no significant GO terms were identified, the gene MLH1 emerged as a critical player due to its association with the late recombination nodule (GO:0005715).

These findings underscore the need for further research to refine the functional annotations of underexplored genes and pathways, enabling a deeper understanding of cancer subtype biology.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

This study uses the DeepInsight framework to transform high-dimensional gene expression data into a pixel-based format for CNN analysis. By integrating DeepInsight with SMOTE, we extended its application to cancer subtype classification and biomarker identification, demonstrating superior performance over DCGN and traditional models like SVM, NNs, LightGBM, and decision trees in terms of F1 score.

A key contribution of this study is the introduction of a multi-class feature selection method using aggregate CAMs within DeepInsight, which allowed for the identification of top genes across breast, lung, and colon cancer datasets. While some of these genes are supported by existing literature, others represent potential novel biomarkers, warranting further investigation. In addition to using DeepInsight, traditional models were employed for gene selection, identifying key genes, which were consistently detected by multiple methods. GO analysis was conducted on the top genes from DeepInsight, and common genes were identified through multiple approaches using the g:Profiler webservice. A limitation of our modified approach is its inability to assign differential weights to the identified genes, a capability offered by traditional models. Likewise, the

g:Profiler webservice treats all genes equally, overlooking the importance of recurrent top genes. Future research should address this by incorporating weighted approaches and exploring tools like Gene Set Enrichment Analysis (GSEA) for more precise GO term analysis.

Moving forward, developing an ensemble methodology that leverages the strengths of various classification models could improve the robustness of cancer subtype identification. Additionally, integrating experimental validation of identified genes and incorporating multi-omics data will be essential for gaining deeper insights into cancer biology. For approaches like DeepInsight, it is imperative to explore strategies to mitigate information loss during the transformation process to ensure the reliability and completeness of the results. Addressing these limitations will enhance the framework's potential for advancing precision oncology and improving cancer subtype classification.

Declarations

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Appendix A Models' Performance

DeepInsight Breast Cancer										
		0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7
Without SMOTE	Accuracy	85.1%	88.9%	85.7%	85.9%	84.9%	85.8%	84.8%	81.8%	81.4%
	F1	85.3%	89.2%	86.1%	86.5%	85.4%	86.2%	85.4%	82.3%	82.8%
	Precision	86.6%	89.8%	87.1%	87.4%	86.3%	87.0%	86.6%	83.6%	85.6%
	AUC	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.97	0.97
	Time	153	149	140	136	131	118	107	96	83
With SMOTE	Accuracy	87.1%	86.9%	86.4%	85.0%	86.6%	84.4%	84.2%	82.1%	80.0%
	F1	87.5%	87.5%	87.3%	85.8%	87.4%	85.4%	85.1%	83.5%	81.2%
	Precision	88.4%	89.2%	88.9%	87.3%	89.0%	87.7%	86.8%	86.1%	83.7%
	AUC	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.97	0.98	0.97	0.96
	Time	314	298	283	269	257	226	197	167	140

Table A1 Performance comparison of the DeepInsight for breast cancer subtype classification with and without SMOTE.

SVM Breast Cancer										
		0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7
Without SMOTE	Accuracy	86.9%	87.0%	86.4%	86.4%	86.2%	85.5%	84.8%	83.5%	81.3%
	F1	86.0%	86.2%	85.4%	85.5%	85.2%	84.2%	83.3%	81.7%	79.0%
	Precision	87.6%	87.4%	86.4%	86.5%	86.3%	85.6%	85.1%	83.9%	81.7%
	AUC	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.97
	Time	160	142	131	124	117	103	87	75	49
With SMOTE	Accuracy	86.3%	86.6%	85.2%	85.3%	85.5%	85.0%	84.1%	82.5%	80.5%
	F1	85.3%	85.8%	84.1%	84.2%	84.3%	83.7%	82.6%	80.5%	77.8%
	Precision	86.9%	86.9%	85.2%	85.4%	85.7%	85.1%	84.4%	83.1%	80.4%
	AUC	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.97	0.97	0.96
	Time	401	371	329	302	276	237	176	131	94

Table A2 Performance comparison of the SVM for breast cancer subtype classification with and without SMOTE.

LightGBM Breast Cancer										
		0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7
Without SMOTE	Accuracy	80.6%	80.9%	79.9%	80.9%	80.3%	79.9%	79.2%	78.4%	78.0%
	F1	83.6%	83.4%	82.7%	83.8%	83.5%	83.2%	82.9%	82.1%	82.2%
	Precision	91.1%	89.9%	89.8%	90.4%	91.0%	90.7%	91.2%	90.6%	91.0%
	AUC	0.96	0.96	0.96	0.96	0.96	0.95	0.95	0.94	0.93
	Time	16	11	11	11	10	8	6	5	4
With SMOTE	Accuracy	84.2%	83.8%	84.0%	83.7%	83.3%	83.6%	82.6%	81.8%	81.4%
	F1	84.0%	83.6%	83.9%	83.5%	83.2%	83.7%	82.8%	82.2%	81.7%
	Precision	84.3%	83.9%	84.2%	83.6%	83.4%	84.1%	83.2%	82.8%	82.2%
	AUC	0.97	0.96	0.95	0.96	0.96	0.95	0.94	0.93	0.92
	Time	39	38	38	35	50	44	30	24	20

Table A3 Performance comparison of the LightGBM for breast cancer subtype classification with and without SMOTE.

NNs Breast Cancer										
		0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7
Without SMOTE	Accuracy	77.4%	75.3%	77.3%	70.3%	73.7%	71.5%	72.6%	69.0%	67.9%
	F1	73.6%	70.6%	73.8%	65.4%	68.6%	65.4%	68.7%	60.4%	60.3%
	Precision	71.2%	69.8%	72.0%	65.1%	68.0%	64.3%	67.9%	60.3%	60.7%
	AUC	0.90	0.88	0.90	0.85	0.86	0.83	0.83	0.84	0.81
	Time	40	37	35	32	32	29	31	24	26
With SMOTE	Accuracy	70.5%	60.5%	61.8%	58.9%	57.2%	44.3%	59.1%	45.6%	45.2%
	F1	68.6%	62.1%	61.6%	55.7%	55.4%	42.5%	55.9%	41.8%	41.4%
	Precision	71.8%	72.4%	69.1%	70.6%	66.9%	54.5%	59.8%	65.5%	61.9%
	AUC	0.89	0.85	0.86	0.81	0.82	0.74	0.80	0.79	0.76
	Time	64	45	49	54	40	20	22	18	18

Table A4 Performance comparison of the NNs for breast cancer subtype classification with and without SMOTE.

Decision Tree Breast Cancer										
		0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7
Without SMOTE	Accuracy	66.3%	71.5%	67.5%	69.1%	68.2%	68.9%	69.4%	65.5%	64.3%
	F1	66.1%	73.2%	68.4%	69.7%	68.8%	68.7%	69.8%	65.7%	64.4%
	Precision	67.6%	75.8%	69.8%	71.9%	70.0%	69.0%	70.8%	66.4%	64.8%
	AUC	0.68	0.68	0.62	0.67	0.65	0.75	0.74	0.71	0.72
	Time	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.2
With SMOTE	Accuracy	70.7%	66.4%	68.5%	70.2%	66.8%	68.0%	66.7%	64.6%	64.7%
	F1	70.0%	66.0%	68.2%	69.6%	66.5%	67.5%	66.4%	64.1%	64.5%
	Precision	70.7%	66.1%	68.5%	69.7%	66.8%	67.6%	66.7%	64.4%	64.6%
	AUC	0.78	0.75	0.75	0.77	0.74	0.76	0.75	0.73	0.73
	Time	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	2	2

Table A5 Performance comparison of the Decision Tree for breast cancer subtype classification with and without SMOTE.

DCGN Breast Cancer										
		0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7
Without SMOTE	Accuracy	83.8%	83.0%	80.4%	80.6%	84.1%	81.0%	81.8%	80.2%	79.9%
	F1	81.4%	80.9%	78.4%	77.7%	82.2%	77.9%	79.8%	78.2%	77.2%
	Precision	79.7%	79.6%	77.0%	76.2%	81.1%	76.8%	78.2%	77.0%	75.4%
	AUC	0.94	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.94	0.92	0.93	0.91	0.92
	Time	55	48	44	41	44	38	38	30	26
With SMOTE	Accuracy	87.9%	87.2%	86.2%	86.9%	85.7%	86.4%	86.0%	85.9%	84.4%
	F1	87.5%	87.2%	85.7%	86.7%	85.6%	86.0%	85.5%	85.6%	83.7%
	Precision	88.2%	87.6%	86.4%	87.4%	86.2%	86.6%	86.1%	85.8%	84.4%
	AUC	0.96	0.96	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.94
	Time	91	137	95	103	85	97	83	72	51

Table A6 Performance comparison of DCGN for breast cancer subtype classification with and without SMOTE.

DeepInsight Colon Cancer										
		0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7
Without SMOTE	Accuracy	83.4%	83.1%	85.8%	84.0%	84.9%	81.8%	84.1%	80.4%	80.3%
	F1	84.4%	82.7%	86.7%	85.4%	86.3%	83.5%	86.0%	83.8%	84.1%
	Precision	86.6%	83.7%	88.3%	87.5%	88.2%	85.9%	89.1%	89.1%	90.4%
	AUC	0.95	0.95	0.96	0.96	0.96	0.96	0.96	0.95	0.94
	Time	91	87	83	81	78	74	68	64	57
With SMOTE	Accuracy	86.3%	83.8%	85.2%	86.3%	85.2%	85.4%	83.6%	81.5%	78.2%
	F1	87.5%	85.4%	87.1%	88.4%	86.9%	87.1%	85.8%	84.0%	82.6%
	Precision	89.7%	87.7%	90.4%	91.3%	89.4%	90.3%	89.5%	89.2%	91.0%
	AUC	0.96	0.96	0.95	0.96	0.96	0.96	0.95	0.95	0.93
	Time	167	158	150	143	137	124	107	93	79

Table A7 Performance comparison of the DeepInsight for colon cancer subtype classification with and without SMOTE.

SVM Colon Cancer										
		0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7
Without SMOTE	Accuracy	86.9%	88.1%	88.1%	87.4%	85.2%	86.1%	85.3%	85.3%	85.0%
	F1	85.1%	86.4%	86.7%	85.7%	83.6%	84.5%	83.2%	83.0%	82.0%
	Precision	84.1%	85.9%	86.5%	85.0%	83.0%	84.5%	83.7%	83.7%	84.0%
	AUC	0.94	0.94	0.93	0.94	0.93	0.92	0.88	0.88	0.86
	Time	22	15	14	13	12	11	8	7	6
With SMOTE	Accuracy	85.1%	86.2%	86.7%	85.3%	83.3%	84.2%	83.9%	83.6%	82.2%
	F1	83.1%	84.0%	85.0%	83.2%	81.4%	82.3%	81.4%	80.7%	78.5%
	Precision	82.5%	84.3%	85.3%	83.1%	81.4%	82.7%	82.6%	83.1%	83.0%
	AUC	0.92	0.92	0.93	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.91	0.88	0.88
	Time	48	42	38	34	31	39	20	13	10

Table A8 Performance comparison of the SVM for colon cancer subtype classification with and without SMOTE.

LightGBM Colon Cancer										
		0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7
Without SMOTE	Accuracy	77.1%	78.1%	78.3%	79.8%	78.8%	75.9%	71.6%	70.6%	70.0%
	F1	82.3%	83.9%	85.0%	85.4%	84.3%	83.1%	80.0%	80.2%	80.0%
	Precision	92.7%	94.1%	95.4%	94.7%	94.4%	95.3%	95.1%	97.0%	97.2%
	AUC	0.90	0.92	0.87	0.89	0.90	0.90	0.84	0.84	0.83
	Time	9	3	3	2	2	2	2	2	1
With SMOTE	Accuracy	80.6%	82.7%	85.5%	82.6%	82.9%	80.1%	81.1%	80.7%	78.8%
	F1	83.1%	84.0%	85.0%	83.2%	81.4%	80.3%	81.2%	81.3%	78.8%
	Precision	82.2%	82.8%	86.8%	83.8%	84.5%	80.7%	82.0%	82.3%	79.0%
	AUC	0.91	0.91	0.94	0.88	0.90	0.89	0.87	0.88	0.87
	Time	12	12	11	10	10	7	6	4	4

Table A9 Performance comparison of the LightGBM for colon cancer subtype classification with and without SMOTE.

NNs Colon Cancer										
		0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7
Without SMOTE	Accuracy	64.6%	73.1%	72.2%	74.4%	70.3%	73.6%	73.6%	72.0%	71.5%
	F1	59.3%	66.6%	69.6%	70.2%	65.7%	68.4%	70.5%	66.4%	66.3%
	Precision	55.1%	68.4%	68.2%	67.5%	65.4%	65.0%	72.2%	63.1%	68.9%
	AUC	0.79	0.83	0.83	0.81	0.80	0.79	0.80	0.74	0.79
	Time	25.6	24.9	24.9	25.1	25.4	24.8	26.9	24.2	26.1
With SMOTE	Accuracy	63.4%	49.2%	48.7%	26.7%	59.6%	56.5%	50.9%	32.9%	56.4%
	F1	63.2%	48.0%	51.4%	30.0%	61.4%	59.7%	47.4%	30.4%	58.3%
	Precision	77.8%	60.0%	61.5%	58.9%	71.2%	69.4%	59.3%	59.1%	66.7%
	AUC	0.82	0.70	0.65	0.69	0.77	0.72	0.71	0.62	0.64
	Time	20	18	11	12	14	12	10	9	9

Table A10 Performance comparison of the NNs for colon cancer subtype classification with and without SMOTE.

Decision Tree Colon Cancer										
		0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7
Without SMOTE	Accuracy	66.3%	71.5%	67.5%	69.1%	68.2%	65.8%	69.7%	66.8%	67.5%
	F1	66.0%	73.2%	68.4%	69.7%	68.8%	65.8%	70.2%	67.6%	69.3%
	Precision	67.6%	75.8%	69.8%	71.9%	70.0%	66.3%	71.1%	69.1%	72.1%
	AUC	0.68	0.68	0.62	0.67	0.65	0.66	0.69	0.62	0.62
	Time	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1
With SMOTE	Accuracy	66.9%	73.1%	74.2%	66.3%	69.5%	62.9%	68.0%	64.8%	61.0%
	F1	65.8%	72.8%	73.8%	65.4%	68.5%	62.4%	68.0%	64.6%	60.4%
	Precision	67.1%	74.0%	74.3%	65.6%	68.2%	62.8%	68.3%	64.9%	61.1%
	AUC	0.67	0.72	0.69	0.65	0.68	0.62	0.64	0.63	0.61
	Time	9	8	8	7	6	1	1	1	0

Table A11 Performance comparison of the Decision Tree for colon cancer subtype classification with and without SMOTE.

DCGN Colon Cancer										
		0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7
Without SMOTE	Accuracy	84.0%	83.5%	81.7%	83.0%	80.2%	80.3%	78.4%	81.6%	81.0%
	F1	82.9%	80.7%	77.7%	80.1%	79.8%	76.9%	76.6%	80.2%	79.2%
	Precision	83.0%	81.2%	76.1%	78.6%	80.4%	75.2%	78.6%	80.5%	78.9%
	AUC	0.90	0.91	0.91	0.88	0.88	0.89	0.87	0.87	0.87
	Time	36	26	24	25	27	20	19	17	18
With SMOTE	Accuracy	81.1%	85.0%	85.5%	84.0%	83.1%	83.5%	83.5%	83.1%	82.7%
	F1	80.6%	83.9%	84.9%	82.8%	82.3%	82.9%	82.7%	82.5%	81.4%
	Precision	81.2%	83.3%	84.5%	82.4%	82.2%	83.1%	82.8%	82.1%	80.9%
	AUC	0.91	0.92	0.92	0.90	0.89	0.90	0.89	0.89	0.88
	Time	48	62	51	47	52	43	46	36	31

Table A12 Performance comparison of DCGN for colon cancer subtype classification with and without SMOTE.

DeepInsight Lung Cancer									
	0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7
Accuracy	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	99.9%	100.0%	99.9%	100.0%	100.0%	99.7%
F1	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	99.9%	100.0%	99.9%	100.0%	100.0%	99.7%
Precision	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	99.9%	100.0%	99.9%	100.0%	100.0%	99.7%
AUC	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
Time	100	97	95	90	89	82	78	70	65
SVM Lung Cancer									
	0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7
Accuracy	99.8%	99.6%	99.6%	99.3%	99.2%	99.2%	99.2%	98.9%	98.2%
F1	99.8%	99.6%	99.6%	99.3%	99.2%	99.2%	99.2%	98.9%	98.2%
Precision	99.8%	99.6%	99.6%	99.3%	99.2%	99.2%	99.2%	98.9%	98.2%
AUC	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	99.9%
Time	26	22	21	20	19	17	14	12	9
LightGBM Lung Cancer									
	0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7
Accuracy	99.4%	99.6%	99.8%	99.9%	99.7%	99.7%	99.1%	99.0%	99.4%
F1	99.4%	99.6%	99.8%	99.9%	99.7%	99.7%	99.1%	99.0%	99.4%
Precision	99.4%	99.6%	99.8%	99.9%	99.7%	99.7%	99.1%	99.1%	99.4%
AUC	99.4%	99.6%	99.8%	99.9%	99.7%	99.7%	99.1%	99.0%	99.4%
Time	8	7	7	7	7	7	4	4	3
NNs Lung Cancer									
	0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7
Accuracy	98.6%	98.2%	99.3%	98.2%	97.6%	98.8%	98.4%	96.5%	94.9%
F1	98.6%	98.2%	99.3%	98.2%	97.6%	98.8%	98.4%	96.5%	94.9%
Precision	98.6%	98.3%	99.3%	98.2%	97.6%	98.8%	98.4%	96.6%	95.2%
AUC	98.5%	98.2%	99.3%	98.1%	97.5%	98.8%	98.4%	96.5%	94.8%
Time	15	13	13	12	12	13	11	9	8
Decision Tree Lung Cancer									
	0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7
Accuracy	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	99.8%	99.8%	99.6%
F1	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	99.8%	99.8%	99.6%
Precision	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	99.8%	99.8%	99.6%
AUC	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	99.8%	99.8%	99.6%
Time	3	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1
DCGN Lung Cancer									
	0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7
Accuracy	100.0%	99.5%	99.3%	99.3%	99.3%	99.4%	99.2%	99.1%	98.2%
F1	100.0%	99.5%	99.3%	99.3%	99.3%	99.4%	99.2%	99.1%	98.2%
Precision	100.0%	99.5%	99.3%	99.4%	99.3%	99.4%	99.2%	99.1%	98.2%
AUC	100.0%	99.4%	99.3%	99.3%	99.3%	99.4%	99.2%	99.1%	98.2%
Time (ms)	67	67	61	74	59	55	57	45	39

Table A13 Performance comparison of all the models for lung cancer subtype classification without SMOTE.

Appendix B Top Genes

Breast Cancer					
SVM	NNs	LightGBM	Deciosn Trees	DCGN	DeepInsight
IGFL3	CRCT1	CEP55	MRGPRF	IL28B	CHST14
MROH9	SLC47A1	GATA3	THOC5	DSCR4	MYOZ1
KRT18P55	UBXN2A	ENTREP1	EVA1C	PNLIPRP1	RAB40A
OR4C3	AQP12A	MIA	RPS7	CFC1B	ARHGEF25
POTEG	NTMT2	ABHD15	SLC15A1	CSAG1	KIF7
SPINK4	VAX1	CENPN	ZNF117	KRTAP4-12	LTBP3
OR4F5	PSAT1	CCDC170	MYBPC1	PPY2	NLGN2
CELA3B	MAPT	ESR1	DUSP4	SLC22A6	ACTG2
ASZ1	SNORA58	FOXA1	DBNDD2	OR6C75	HSPB2
LCE6A	OR6C1	UBE2Q2P2	SLC2A9	OR6Q1	LIMS2
RBMXL3	CMBL	CENPA	ZGRF1	PDX1	SMIM10
SPRR4	SPRR4	ERBB2	FSCN1	PRAMEF9	GAS6
PGK2	PVR	KIAA0825	TDGF1	PRAMEF18	PNMA8B
FAM71B	TLX3	HAPLN4	BBOF1	OR6C1	SERTAD4-AS
PDX1	PRAMEF18	HAAO	SYT8	AQP12A	CRLF1
MAGEB18	LCE6A	LMX1B	BCL2	SPRR4	WTIP
PPY2P	KRTAP4-12	MPHOSPH6	TMEM71	OR5M9	DZIP1L
EFNA2	OR5M9	GRB7	EXO1	OR2B2	ACTA2
CNBD1	PDX1	NEK2	PLEKHG1	CETN1	NOG
FAM9A	PRAMEF9	CDKN3	CENPN	SNORA58	TAGLN

Table B14 In breast cancer, certain genes, such as LCE6A and CENPN, are identified by multiple models. DeepInsight has uniquely identified genes such as CHST14, MYOZ1, and RAB40A, which are not highlighted by other models.

Lung Cancer					
SVM	NNs	LightGBM	Deciosn Trees	DCGN	DeepInsight
TBATA	RBMS2	TMPRSS11E	FOXI1	OPRM1	DACT3
LINC01300	DCAF13P3	UBE2Q2P2	FOXN4	HIST1H2BB	MYL9
C2orf83	SNHG9	AARS1	FOXN3	OR10J3	JPH2
OR6S1	ZKSCAN2	ABCA3	FOXN2	KRTAP4-1	COL8A1
SNORA50C	SNORA21	ACCSL	FOXN1	SNORA3	TIMP3
TCF23	OPRD1	A4GALT	FOXM1	TTL8	MATN3
LCE2D	SPMIP7	JUP	FOXL2	TYR	STMN2
ZAN	WAPL	OLFML2A	FOXH1	ZIM3	OPCML
C4orf51	TTYH2	SPINT3	FOXL1	PEBP4	DIO3
KRTAP4-1	TTY8	LRRC1	FOXK1	TCF23	ZNF423
IQCF6	OR14I1	OR11G2	FOXJ3	SNORA76	SLC16A2
CATSPER4	TOPAZ1	ACTR6	FOXJ2	OR4D1	NRK
H2BC3	SPINK9	SPINK14	FOXJ1	ZAN	LINC00922
SNORA56	OR2AG2	BAG4	FOXI3	SNORA56	NXPE2
VWC2L	TTYH1	PPL	FOXI2	VWC2L	PLXNA4
ZIM3	PREX1	ABCD3	FOXK2	PRHOXNB	TNN
PRAMEF12	OR13J1	GATA3	ZZZ3	PRAMEF12	PLXDC1
OR4D1	OPRM1	ADRA1D	LRIT2	OR11G2	AXL
URAD	SNORA3A	LINC02532	C10orf53	CATSPER4	SPX
OR11G2	TCF19	TRIM75	RBM1J	IQCF6	RSPO3

Table B15 In lung cancer, DeepInsight again provided a distinct set of genes, like NRK.

Colon Cancer					
SVM	NNs	LightGBM	Deciosn Trees	DCGN	DeepInsight
PRPS1L1	NSD2	ATP5F1A	FSD1	ACTG1	CFAP68
NALF2	MTRR	PHF23	TPO	UBB	LRRC23
SP9	GDF9	MLH1	STK19	HSPB1	SFT2D3
MLH1	DOK1	DEFA5	SNAPC1	FTL	ABHD1
APOC1P1	ZBTB11-AS1	AP3B1	ZEB2	TMSB10	C1orf56
SNORA68	RTF2	UBE2Q2P2	ANXA4	PDIA3	EIF4EBP3
TTC29	DDAH2	BAX	LAMC3	HSPD1	TAPT1-AS1
DKK1	CREBRF	NSMCE1	MGAM	HLA-B	PRSS30P
ALOX12P2	CNTD1	SEZ6L	MPP3	KRT19	PYGB
EPYC	R3HDM1	RAB22A	MRPL53	HSPA5	CELF5
CBY2	CEP170P1	SRC	ZNF512	UBC	MMP24
SEC14L4	TRIM16	STAC3	DHRS7	HLA-A	ENTPD6
TCP11	ADGRF5	AMACR	PRR15	HSPA1A	TMEM270
KLK8	ATXN7L3B	STX12	LZIC	H3F3B	LINC00910
CCDC198	HIST1H4J	METAP2	ASPHD2	HSP90B1	PFN4
ESRG	GRIP2	RPS27L	EVA1C	RPL19	ACTR3C
STYXL2	SUPT7L	GAS2L1	TRIP4	CLTC	NEU1
ZSCAN10	UBE2E3	DDX27	KRT6A	KRT18	SLC22A3
IGFL4	C5orf46	SPATA18	RNF32-DT	HSP90AA1	RALY
CFAP47	GOLGA8IP	TRAPPC2	ZBTB12	KRT8	FBXL12

Table B16 In colon cancer, DeepInsight identified unique genes like CFAP68, LRRC23, and several others.

Appendix C GO context analysis

Fig. C1 GO enrichment analysis of top and repeat genes in breast (upper) and lung (below) cancer subtypes. Each point represents a GO term, with the circle size showing the number of associated genes and the y-axis showing the negative logarithm of the adjusted p-value.